

MYTHS AND REALITIES ABOUT HYPERTENSION: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF RECOMMENDATIONS OF RESEARCH JOURNALS AND MEDICAL ASSOCIATIONS

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Abstract

The goal of the study was to manipulate the way that associations for hypertension disease and research journal articles describe suggestions for patient diets and safety. The study covered the selection, generalization, deletion, and construction processes that are used to alter the discourse and delete information through association recommendations. For the critical discourse analysis of the recommendations made by the research articles and associations, the researcher used Van Dijk's macrostructure model of discourse as an instrument. For the analysis of the data derived from articles and other web publications, Excel and AntConc were also employed. The investigation included 10 research articles in total and the recommendations of 3 main medical associations employed. Data presented in the form of tables and charts for depth of understanding. The study's findings demonstrated that associations engage in this activity because they are constrained from offering a full discourse by several constraints. In this way, the discourse surrounding hypertension sickness is distorted endangering the health of sufferers.

Keywords: Hypertension, Medical, Journals, Discourse, Research

Introduction

The Hypertension is often known as a high pulse. This is a state in which the pressure of the blood is too high. Hypertension happens when the small veins of the body, called arterioles constrict, causing the blood to use excessive strain against the vessel dividers and pressuring the heart to work

strictly to keep up with the pressure. Even though the heart and veins can withstand an extended pulse for months or even years, the heart eventually grows and becomes weak to the point of growth. Vein damage to the kidneys, mind, and eyes is also a possibility. Hypertension is also known as high or increased blood pressure. Circulatory strain is a condition in which the veins are constantly tense. Blood is transported. The vessels carry blood from the heart to all parts of the body. The force of blood pressing against the dividers of veins as it is drained by the heart causes circulatory strain. The harder the heart has to syphon, the higher the strain. Hypertension is a serious condition that can lead to heart, brain, kidney, and other organ failures. It is a major cause of sudden death all over the world, affecting as many as one out of every four males and one out of every ten women. The illness affects 5 women out of a billion people. Hypertension affects an idea 26 percent of the population of world, or 972 million people, and the commonness is expected to rise to 29 percent by 2025. In poverty and low-income countries, the burden of hypertension is disproportionately felt.

Types of Hypertensions

- **Primary hypertension:** It is the most serious kind of hypertension. It is also known as essential hypertension, and it affects most adults. It's thought to be a genetic and lifestyle issue.
- **Secondary hypertension:** The secondary kind of hypertension affects about 5 to 10% of the population and is most common in adults aged 18 to 50.

Hypertension Subtypes

- **Hypertension that is resistant to treatment**

Approximately 10% of people with this type of blood pressure have it at an early stage, making it difficult to regulate and requiring a lot of meditation.

- **Malignant Hypertension**

The most serious and emergency blood pressure is around 180/130, according to experts, and this type of blood pressure is often the cause of various organ damage, with the rate of these patients being greater in black individuals.

Recommendations by Different Medical Associations

- AHA Suggestions for Meditation/Treatment by Medical Advisories (American Heart Association)
- Medline. Plus offers advice from the Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2021)
- National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute Recommendations (2020) Meditations

Research Objectives

This study has the following objectives;

- To analyse the major difference between the discourse of medical association's recommendations and the research journal's recommendations
- To investigate hidden realities based on Van Dijk's model of discourse
- To understand the vocabulary and syntactic description of the research journals articles recommendations and associations recommendations
- To discuss all the major parts of Van Dijk's model of discourse

Research Questions

This study has the following questions;

- What are the major differences between the discourse of medical association's recommendations and the research journal's recommendations?
- How to manipulate hidden realities based on Van Dijk's model of discourse?
- How to analyse the vocabulary and syntactic description of the research journal articles recommendations and hypertension associations recommendations?
- How Generalisation, Selection, Deletion, and Construction is done by both the research journals and the medical association's recommendations?

Literature Review

Discourse and Language

Discourse as an area explores discussion between individuals who use the parallel contract's speech. Furthermore, discourse leads to the linguistics of language use as a means of containing social interactions, especially the examination of aligned speech or written discourse that happens Hamuddin, Dakowska (2001). Van Dijk (2000) shows how ideology influences both the positive and negative depiction of particular populations. According to Van Dijk (2000), ideology plays a serious role in the positive representation of some groups and the bad image of others. Politicians and the media frequently use the SELF and OTHERS debate. In other words, members of the in-group are always depicted positively, whereas members of the out-group are always depicted negatively. Michel Foucault's work is important when considering how power is exercised over the (female, reproductive) body in Western civilization (Rail & Harvey, 1995, p. 165).

Power, according to Foucault, is a result of speech that operates inside daily exchanges between people and institutions, rather than something controlled by specific persons or organizations and utilized to oppress others (Burr, 2003, p. 68). Another noteworthy example of the contribution that discourse-based techniques can make is Skillington (1998). In his research, he investigates the novelty of Dublin's city center using a textual-focused analysis based on Fairclough. According to Skillington, representative and referential discourses have developed a narrow-minded ruling paradigm that encourages a strict boundary between the community and isolated space,

consequently making it tougher to distinguish between the two. Cognitive analysis can be reduced to a few main rules and categories. There are numerous cognitive studies that show how numerous circumstantial or textual manipulations might alter understanding, but reviewing these (for broad accounts of) is apart the scope of this paper. Britton & Graesser, 1996 & Kintsch, 1998; Van Dijk, 1998; Britton and Graesser, 1996; Britton and Graesser, 1996; Britton and Graesser, Van Oostendorp and Goldman (Van Oostendorp and Kintsch, 1983 & Van Oostendorp and Kintsch, 1999).

While manipulation can distress the making or modification of rare personal cognitive representations, the overall goal of organising discourse is to limited shared social presentations among clusters of people because these are the most powerful people's actions and words are influenced by their social beliefs in a variety of situations a period of time that is relatively long.

Critical Discourse Analysis

According to Trask (2007), CDA is interested in resolving questions like why was this text generated in the first place. What kind of individuals or societies is it aimed at? What is the reason for this? Is there a hidden agenda behind the writer's or speaker's words? What implicit assumptions and prejudices are present in the text? Non-Indigenous people investigating Indigenous Peoples and environments face complex ethical challenges regarding proper roles, obligations, and approaches. There were many writers with unquestionable power, sociocultural position, and attitude while evaluating Aboriginal and Torres Strait Inhabitant Individuals' speech and text, for example. While directing CDA investigation in Native contexts, non-Indigenous academics should look into three areas: critical reflexivity, colonist influence analysis, and obvious anti-racists. (Julia McCartan, Julie Brimblecombe b, Karen Adams, 2022).

Politicians and media proprietors, according to Joseph (2006), utilize propaganda, deception, and manipulation in their speeches to achieve political aims and interests on the one hand and to devalue or discredit their opponents on the other. Text producers, particularly politicians, utilize language in a specific way to achieve their goals by employing a variety of manipulative methods. The goal of CDA is to uncover the true intentions of text producers toward laypeople. In this scenario, it's crucial to figure out who's to blame.

Discourse and Society

Cots (2006) offered several exercises to be surveyed in coaching reading skills to disclose the claim of (CDA) in language teaching. Cots, in particular, and by Fairclough's (1992) analytical model, questions with three sets offered, each about three unlike degrees of text investigation, specifically practices in social, conversational, and textual settings. He was sure that through asking the inquiries, he was able to learn more about himself. Teachers will be able to examine a critical approach to language use. The impact of critical discourse analysis on pupils' reading skills was studied by

Rahimi and Sharififar (2015). As a reading text, the pupils were given one of Obama's political speeches. The students had previously been asked to study the text. Based on the competence of the pupil's hard work in analyzing the text as well as their overall performance through a questionnaire, participants' perceptions of the impact of CDA on their performance were acquired.

The researchers concluded CDA increased pupils' critical thinking skills. As an example, they proposed, as a result of the study, that instead of delivering factual materials, both Ideologically charged reading texts should be preferred by instructors and curriculum designers. According to them, teachers should concentrate on inferential questions in the classroom. These three aspects text/context orientation, the standardized repertory of discourse theory, and practical rehearsal produce temptation for new academics to structure their work in this way if they want it to be noticed.

Even if interventionist critique has been questioned (e.g., Widdowson, 1995; Schegloff, 1997), the respective discourse on discourse analysis and critique must be recreated. In some ways, a discourse specialist cannot help but be compelled to take up these problems and place oneself about them. To make ready the students for positive communication overall and to help them understand more fully the implications of their reading in EFL reading classes, Lezberg & Hilferty (1978) suggested giving more attention to plays as analysis of texts, presumptuous that the field includes "those covert elements of social interaction which control and transcend the meaning of each discrete word, sentence, or paragraph" (p. 49 & 50). Also, as a reading workout using texts from the present newspaper.

They showed certain tasks such as browsing, scanning, and reading newspapers and magazines. Before-reading and after-reading exercises, as well as some reading skill exercises, are examples of activities. Timed reading tasks, for example. They anticipated that by practicing these workouts, they would be able to students would no longer be afraid of reading materials. Discourse studies are concerned with the work of language and formation of the real society. We use Hajer's (1995; 2006) discourse method. We define discourse as "an ensemble of thoughts, ideas, concepts, and categorizations through which meaning is assigned to social and physical realities, and which is produced and reproduced in an identifiable set of behaviors," as defined by Hajer (2009; p. 59–60). Through an argumentative lens, Hajer examines the usage of language in political activities. Policy issues such as the upcoming days of hegemony. Supply has become the focus of debates in which various societal actors attempt to persuade others to understand the policy issue in their way.

Research Gap

This research paper will focus on Myths and Realities About Hypertension; A Critical Discourse Analysis of Recommendations of Journals and Medical Associations.

Research Methodology

The research is a mixed method research as both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used by the researcher for the data collection and analysis. Firstly, the researcher applied the discourse model of Van Dijk to compare the discourse of recommendations by research journal articles with those of hypertension associations recommendations. The researcher also used AntConc for the comparison on the basis of vocabulary (at word level) and also used Google Excel sheets for the analysis of the data and for the graphical representation of the data. Web-documents (research articles & websites) were used by the researcher for the data and then analysed the data by the application of Van Dijk discourse model and categorised the data into the categories defined by Van Dijk that are; deletion, selection, generalisation and construction. Secondly, after converting data into quantitative form the researcher will use different tables graphs and pie charts for depth interpretation and manipulation of the recommendations of research articles and medical associations.

Results and Discussion

According to Ven Dijk's model to much selection (**21%**) is done in the recommendations both by the advisories and journals. There are some points which are selected due to certain objectives from both the sides through which we can judge the settings. Secondly construction (**19%**) is also done at a large extent because there are many suggestions and recommendations which are constructed by both the sides to step by step promote their targets. Thirdly generalisation is another fact which is also done in both the texts but it is still less as compare to Construction (**16%**) and Selection. Lastly Deletion (**16%**) is also having points as compare to all other rules of the Ven Dijk's model.

Figure: 1. Van Dijk's model.

So, to answer the first question of our research we concluded that both the research journals recommendations and medical associations recommendations used different discourse in order to establish their own point of view. Medical associations used medical and technical language regarding hypertension and on the other hand research journals also having different criteria and language variations about the disease, both the sides tried to promote their agenda. Second question answered that all the manipulation which is done by both the recommendations of journals and medical associations is investigated through Van Dijk's model of discourse.

Data description is properly presented in the form of tables and charts for depth understandings, moreover all the phenomena behind both the research journals and medical associations recommendations is revealed through the application of Van Dijk's model of discourse. Third and the main objective of the research illustrated that the language variations and language construction is entirely different of both the sides. To expose the syntactic variations, language description and vocabulary of research and medical recommendations Van Dijk's model of discourse applied on the syntax level of both the sides in order to attain the real intentions of the producers. Last question which is entirely focused on promoting the brands and associations is exposed through the Van Dijk's model of discourse. Through the major parts of the Van Dijk's model including generalisation, deletion, construction and selection all the manipulation is done from both the sides is investigated. All these major differences is pointed out through AntConc, frequency and by using facts and figures in order to establish a statistical analysis of both the sides.

To wind up the whole discussion it is concluded that advisories and associations throwing dust in population's eyes just only to promote their businesses and wealth Trask (2007). This conspiracy is being done at large extent because they want to control the world according to their own version and this process of recommending Irregular meditations can lead towards further diseases Hamuddin, Dakowska (2001). And from this point of view, we can judge that all the brands and medical associations are promoting the theory of Materialism (Karl Marx) and all its evidences are clearly mentioned in the recommendations to promote their business targets (Julia McCartan, Julie Brimblecombe b, Karen Adams, 2022). All this conspiracy is portraying a clear view of capitalist and rich community that how they are deceiving the local population? All these events are aligned with different concepts and theories (Materialism & Capitalism) of elites Hajer's (1995; 2006). First, they will develop different diseases within the labs and later on they introduce different vaccines and meditations to support and promote their personal businesses Van Oostendorp and Kintsch, (1999). This game is not only being played by a community of any specific region rather this trap is set by different communities within different nations Lezberg & Hilferty (1978). Apart from this we can judge that there is a clear difference regarding suggestions and recommendations and this conspiracy is exposed through discursive analysis from both the advisories and journals and at the end results and suggestions from both the sides showed a clear difference.

Conclusion

Critical discourse analysis is utilised in a variety of disciplines and fields. The medical profession is widely perceived as always providing accurate information and transmitting meaning without modifying the facts to fit their aims or intentions. The macrostructure criteria of Van Dijk have been used to analyse medical associations and research articles. The study's premise was confirmed there has been increased deletion and generalisation of relevant facts in medical groups' recommendations. It has been discovered that organisations have kept their information private by abstracting the details and making them too generic in order to conceal the sponsors behind this technique because associations typically link with corporations.

The support of capitalism is the cause of the deletion and generalisation of propositions. Due to the fact that business organisations genuinely support both the food markets and the medical health associations, capitalist theory is also reflecting the medical discourse in the way that food markets have become globally diversified. These companies will suffer if medical groups impose any restrictions on processed foods, and they cannot afford such losses. The national and international medical organisations are sponsored by businesses since, in accordance with capitalism theory (Chun, 2017), companies are created to maximise profits. The vague, constrictive, and generalised discourse of associations is actually caused by this. Additionally, the medical administrators are associated with numerous brands, the creators of medical discourse try to exert a significant effect of their underlying views and goals on the public. Since research articles are not affiliated with any brand or pharmaceutical company, their recommendations are accurate and unambiguous.

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